

Subject 1: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis on Risk Factors for Sporadic Food-Borne Illnesses

Part VII: Norovirus infection

Ursula Gonzales-Barron and Vasco Cadavez
CIMO Mountain Research Centre, School of Agriculture, Polytechnic Institute of Braganza,
Portugal

On request from the French Agency for Food, Environmental and Occupational Health and Safety (ANSES) in coordination with Pauline Kooh and Moez Sanaa

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The quality assessment stage was passed by 14 primary studies investigating risk factors for sporadic infection with *norovirus*, which were conducted between 1993 and 2014. From these, eight studies investigated exposures in children/infants, while other eight focused on the mixed population. These primary studies provided a total of 105 ORs which were hierarchically categorised for meta-analysis. Of these, 83% of the meta-analytical data were produced by case-control and cohort studies undertaken in the Netherlands (35 ORs), UK (19 ORs), Vietnam (13 ORs), China (10 ORs) and Mexico (10 ORs). Ten primary studies employed an unmatched experimental design and produced a total of 47 ORs. From these, 21 reported ORs were not adjusted by any confounder (i.e., crude ORs by Chi-square test), while the others were adjusted by using unconditional logistic regression (26 ORs). On the other hand, only four studies employed a matched experimental design, providing for meta-analysis a total of 58 ORs. From these, most of them were adjusted ORs estimated by logistic regressions (38 ORs). After methodological quality assessment, two primary studies were marked as being below standards, which yielded a total of 9 potentially-biased ORs. With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused more on the multiple pathways of exposure (91 ORs) than on host specific factors (12) and travel (2).

According to this meta-analysis study, the most important determinants of *norovirus* infection in the mixed population are the host-specific factor of suffering from a chronic immunosuppressive disease (overall OR=8.17; 95% CI: 3.26 – 20.47) and direct person-to-person contagion (overall OR=3.01; 95% CI: 1.71 – 5.47), which bear discernibly greater association with *norovirus* infection than consumption of seafood (overall OR=2.27; 95% CI: 1.30 – 3.97) and foods as a whole (overall OR=1.57; 95% CI: 1.24 – 1.98). The odds of acquiring *norovirus* from drinking water (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 0.97 – 3.17) is comparable to that of the host-specific factor of suffering from other medical conditions

(overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 0.77 – 3.53); while contact with pets was not found to be a source of *norovirus* (overall OR=0.67; 95% CI: 0.54 – 0.83) in the mixed population.

In children, direct transmission person to person (overall OR=6.43; 95% CI: 3.77 – 10.97) is the most important route for acquiring *norovirus* infection, followed by consumption of unspecified suspicious food (data from China, Vietnam and Mexico; overall OR=4.54; 95% CI: 3.16 – 6.53). The general environmental-related exposures are determinant of *norovirus* infection in children (pooled OR=1.56; 95% CI: 1.16 – 2.13) – although at a significantly lower level of association than that of person-to-person contagion. Children living on a farm (overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.18 – 2.27) are as exposed to *norovirus* as those attending day care (overall OR=1.32; 95% CI: 0.96 – 1.81) whereas drinking water bears only a minor association with *norovirus* infection (overall OR=1.10; 95% CI: 0.88 – 1.38). Whilst keeping poor handwashing habits (overall OR=1.78; 95% CI: 0.63 – 5.04) could not be proven to be a factor facilitating the infection with *norovirus* in children, consuming beef and chicken is not a source of disease (overall OR=0.74; 95% CI: 0.84 – 1.02).

3. Results

3.7 *Norovirus*

3.7.1 *Descriptive statistics*

In the systematic review of risk factors pertaining to human infection with *norovirus*, a total of 672 bibliographic sources were identified using the keywords in the five search engines, from which 99 passed the full assessment for eligibility comprising case-control and cohort studies from both sporadic illnesses and outbreaks (Figure 1). A total of 85 fully-documented case-control studies investigated the source(s) of outbreaks and were kept in the JabRef file as their data can be readily extracted. In this study, meta-analysis was undertaken using 14 primary studies – case-control and cohort studies – with focus on sporadic disease (Figure 1). These published studies were conducted in years spanning from 1993 and 2014. Table 1 compiles a list of the case-control/cohort studies along with their main features. The eligible studies jointly provided 105 odds-ratios which were categorised for meta-analysis. A total of 55 ORs were retrieved from 3 case-control studies performed before the year 2000, while 50 ORs were excerpted from 11 studies performed after 2000. Meta-analytical data were obtained from case-control and cohort studies conducted in 10 countries, although studies from 5 countries provided ~83% of the ORs. These were: Netherlands (35 ORs), UK (19 ORs), Vietnam (13 ORs), China (10 ORs) and Mexico (10 ORs) (Figure 2, top left).

Eight studies investigated risk factors for *norovirus* infection in children – producing 55 ORs – whereas eight studies focused on the mixed population, yielding other 50 ORs. As a rule, because of their distinct routes of exposure and susceptibility to *norovirus*, meta-analyses were adjusted separately for the mixed and children population. Data from both age groups were merged only when ORs belonging to the children population were too few to run a separate meta-analysis model. In all of the primary studies, the *norovirus* cases were laboratory-confirmed. Four case-control studies employed a matched experimental design and produced a total of 58 categorised ORs, which represented 55% of the data. Of these, 32 ORs were computed in multivariate analysis whereas 26 were obtained in univariate analysis. ORs from matched designs were mostly estimated using logistic regressions (27 ORs from unconditional and 15 ORs conditional) and only a few by the simple chi-square test (16).

From the studies that applied an unmatched design (10 studies), mostly cohort studies, a total of 47 ORs were extracted, which constituted 45% of the meta-analytical data. A total of 29 ORs were computed in univariate analysis while 18 in multivariate analysis. The ORs from unmatched designs were estimated using chi-square (21) and UL (26). In none of the primary studies, authors obtained MH-estimates adjusted by a confounder's strata within a frequency-matched experimental design. Bringing together the matched and unmatched designs, 47 extracted ORs (44.7% of the data) were not adjusted by any confounder (crude ORs), while 58 ORs (55.3%) were adjusted using only logistic regressions (Figure 3).

During methodological quality assessment, the ORs extracted from two case-control studies (Enserink et al., 2015; and Henke-Gendo et al., 2009) were marked as being possibly affected by bias. The rationale for assigning potential-for-bias status to the association measures extracted from Enserink et al. (2015) related to the distinct statistical approach employed which was based on a Poisson model. The ORs obtained from Henke-Gendo et al. (2009) were regarded as potentially suffering from selection bias because the cases were defined as

patients with prolonged *norovirus* excretion longer than 10 days or 28 days. These two case-control studies provided 9 potentially-biased ORs whose influence on the meta-analysed OR estimates was appraised by means of the Cook's distance.

Figure 1. Flow chart of literature search for case-control and cohort studies of human *norovirus* infection

*Records kept in JabRef with PDFs files annexed

With regards to the risk factor classes, sporadic illness investigations focused to a greater extent on the multiple pathways of transmission (91 ORs) than on host specific factors (12 ORs) or travel (2 ORs) (Figure 2, bottom left). Within the pathways of transmission (Figure 2, bottom right), person-to-person contact was the route whose association with disease was the most frequently assessed (37 ORs) because direct contagion is the most suspected mode of transmission. Moore et al. (2015) estimated in 62-84% of all reported outbreaks, noroviruses were transmitted directly from person to person. *Norovirus* can be also transmitted indirectly via contaminated food and water. Thus, food consumption routes (28 ORs) and environmental routes (19 ORs) more often appraised than the animal-related routes of transmission (7 ORs). General information on the distribution of the number of ORs available for meta-analysis is presented in Figure 3 by study design, type of analysis, model, type of odds-ratio, study period and potential for bias status.

Figure 2. Distribution of the number of odds-ratios (y-axis) extracted from case-control and cohort studies of sporadic *norovirus* infection by country (top left), population type (top right), risk factor (bottom left) and pathway of exposure (bottom right)

Figure 3. Pie-diagrams of the number of odds-ratios extracted from case-control and cohort studies of sporadic *norovirus* infection by experimental design (top left), analysis type (top right), model type (middle left), odds-ratio type (middle right), study period cut-off year 2000 (bottom left) and assigned potential for bias (bottom right)

Table 1. Characteristics of primary studies investigating risk factors for acquiring sporadic *norovirus* infection included in the meta-analysis

Study ID	Country	Study period	Population	Design	Analysis & model	# cases /controls	Quality Final ORs /removed*
Dai et al. 2009	China	Oct 2003 - Jan 2006	Children	Matched	Uni-UL Multi-UL	112 cases 357 controls	Good 8
Enserink et al. 2015	Netherlands	2010 - 2012	Children	Unmatched	Multi-UL	504 cases 4693 controls	Poor 3
Fretz et al. 2005	Switzerland	2001 - 2003	Mixed	Matched	Uni- CL	73 cases 73 controls	Good 5
Grant et al. 2012	USA	Mar 2002 - Oct 2003	Children	Unmatched	Multi-UL	62 cases 50 controls	Good 1
Henke-Gendo et al. 2012	Germany	Jan 2005 - Jun 2008	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	20 cases 58 controls	Poor 6
Heusinkveld et al. 2016	Netherlands	Apr 2013 - Oct 2014	Children	Unmatched	Multi-UL	60 cases 1843 controls	Good 6
Karsten et al. 2009	Germany	Jan - Dec 2004	Mixed	Unmatched	Multi-UL	186 cases 1399 controls	Good 2
My et al. 2013	Vietnam	May 2009 - Dec 2010	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Multi-UL	242 cases 592 controls	Good 13
Peasey et al. 2004	Mexico	Nov 1993 - Jan 1995	Children	Unmatched	Uni-Chi Uni-UL	83 cases 174 controls	Good 10/1
Phillips et al. 2010	UK	1993 - 1996	Children Mixed	Matched	Multi-UL	81 cases 461 controls 156 cases 1206 controls	Good 19/1
Relié et al. 2015	Serbia	2010 - 2011	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	36 cases 51 controls	Good 1
Tang et al. 2013	Taiwan	Aug 2011 - Jul 2012	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	17 cases 138 controls	Good 3/1
Wit et al. 2003	Netherlands	1999	Mixed Children	Matched	Uni-Chi Multi-CL Uni-Chi Multi-CL	152 cases 152 controls 105 cases 105 controls	Good 26
Xue et al. 1993	China	May 2012 - Aug 2013	Mixed	Unmatched	Uni-Chi	903 cases 3038 controls	Good 2

(*) Number of ORs not included in the meta-analysis for presenting mean values lower than 0.5.

3.7.2 Meta-analysis for host-specific risk factors and travel-, environment-, animal-, food-related and person-to-person pathways of transmission

In the data partitions pertaining to travel, host-specific factors, environmental pathways and food consumption routes of transmission, it was not possible to assess differences in pooled ORs between the two study periods (before and after the year 2000) due to insufficiency of data. However, assessing the effect of study period on the pooled ORs, it was found that the risks of *norovirus* due to animal-related routes ($p=0.807$; Table 4), environmental pathways in

children ($p=0.455$; Table 5B) and person-to-person contagion ($p=0.790$; Table 6B), as measured in the earlier studies (before the year 2000), did not change significantly in the most recent years (after 2000). Therefore, in all of the models adjusted to the data partitions above, the variable “study period” was dropped from the full meta-analysis models, and the ORs were pooled to represent data from both study periods.

For the travel exposure, only two ORs were available, and they were extracted from the same study (Phillips et al., 2010), whereby international travel was evaluated as risk factor for acquiring *norovirus* infection in both children and mixed population in England. Thus, with two ORs coming from the same study, it was not possible to adjust a meta-analysis model, and the pooled OR shown in Table 2 should be rather understood as an average value. On average, people who travelled outside England had 3.622 times (95% CI: 1.742 – 7.546) greater probability of becoming infected with *norovirus* than people who did not travel at all (Table 2). The funnel plot, although devoid of meaning, is shown in Figure 4.

Table 2. Meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for acquiring *norovirus* infection in the mixed (n=1 OR) and children (n=1 OR) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All Travel	1.287	0.3741	2	[0.555 – 2.021]	0.001
(1 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Abroad	1.287	0.3741	2	[0.555 – 2.021]	0.001
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2 (residual)	0.2402				

(*) Pooled OR for All Travel is equal to pooled OR for travel abroad since it was the only subcategory for which data was available

Figure 4. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of travel as a risk factor for *norovirus* infection in combined mixed and children population

As with the travel data partition, meta-analysis on host-specific factors by geographical region could not be undertaken due to very few data points available. On meta-analysis, suffering from a chronic disease (i.e., immunosuppression) or another medical condition (i.e., being a transplant recipient) significantly exacerbated the risk of acquiring *norovirus* infection in the mixed population (overall OR=3.725; 95% CI: 1.660 – 8.356 in Table 3). When the analysis was conducted by subcategory, it became clear that immunosuppression (overall OR=8.174; 95% CI: 3.264 – 20.47) was a more important predisposing factor in the mixed population than being a transplant recipient (overall OR=1.645; 95% CI: 0.767 – 3.529). Poor hygiene habits in Vietnamese and Mexican children could not be proven to predispose them to acquiring *norovirus* infection (overall OR=1.775; 95% CI: 0.625 – 5.038), although this is not conclusive since the extracted ORs in this subcategory were only three (Table 3). Publication bias was evident in both the mixed population (p=0.005) and the children partition (p=0.001) meta-analyses given both the significant effect of study size on the measured ORs and the non-homogeneous distribution of observations within the funnel plots (Figure 5). Such behaviour is likely to arise due to the limited data points found in the literature for the host-specific factors data partition.

Table 3. Meta-analysis of host specific factors for giardiasis in the mixed (n=8) and children population (n=3)

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (3 stud)	All host-specific	1.315	0.412	8	[0.507 – 2.123]	0.001
	Fixed effects					
	Chronic	2.101 ^b	0.468	4	[1.183 – 3.019]	<.0001
	Other med	0.498 ^a	0.389	4	[-0.265 – 1.261]	0.201
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.3576	QE(df=6)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.7630	p=0.007		p<.001	
	Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0001			0.005
	Points removed	0				
Children (2 stud)	All host-specific	0.574	0.532	3	[-0.469 – 1.617]	0.281
	Fixed effects					
	Hygiene	0.574	0.532	3	[-0.469 – 1.617]	0.281
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.7661	QE(df=2)			
	s ² (residual)	1.1017	p=0.004			
	Publication bias	-0.0045	0.0013			0.001
	Points removed	0				

Figure 5. Funnel plot of the meta-analyses of host-specific risk factors for *norovirus* infection in the mixed (left) and children (right) population

Regarding the animal-related pathways of transmission in the mixed population, contact with pets and farm animals, overall, did not appear as an important source of *norovirus* infection in the mixed population of Germany, UK, the Netherlands and Mexico (overall OR=1.198; 95% CI: 0.558 – 2.578; Table 4). However, when the meta-analysis was adjusted in the disaggregated form, contact with farm animals in the children population turned out to be an important source of disease (overall OR=2.680; 95% CI: 1.377 – 5.217) while contact with pets (overall OR=0.674; 95% CI: 0.544 – 0.834; Table 4) was not a significant source of transmission of *norovirus*. Particularly for the exposure of contact with farm animals, such results must be interpreted with caution since the ORs available were too few. Despite this, there was no evidence of publication bias since there was no effect of study size on the published OR measures ($p=0.404$). Furthermore, the funnel plot did not signal any strong evidence of publication bias (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of animal contact pathways as risk factors for *norovirus* infection in the combined mixed and children population

Table 4. Meta-analysis of pathways related to animal contact for acquiring giardiasis in the combined mixed (n=3) and children (n=4) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All animal	0.181	0.464	7	[-0.584 – 0.947]	0.643
(5 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Farm in children	0.986 ^b	0.340	2	[0.320 – 1.652]	0.004
	Pets in mixed/child	-0.395 ^a	0.109	5	[-0.608 – -0.182]	0.001
	Before 2000					0.807
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=5)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.8811	p=0.018		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0004	0.0004			0.404
	Points removed	0				

The meta-analysis on environmental pathways by region showed that in Western Europe, these routes were significantly associated with *norovirus* in the mixed population (pooled OR=1.680; p=0.009) and children (pooled OR=1.614; p<.0001 in Table 5A). In Asia, there was no agreement in pooled ORs between population types: while no association was proven between the overall environmental pathways and *norovirus* infection in Asian children (pooled OR=1.069; p=0.471), strong association was found in the Asian mixed population (pooled OR=3.320; p=0.042). Because of the limited data available, the case-control studies from Asian countries were not removed for the subsequent general meta-analysis.

Table 5A. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring *norovirus* infection by region in the mixed (n=6) and children (n=12) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
Asia	1.200	0.589	2	[0.045 – 2.354]	0.042
West Europe	0.519	0.198	4	[0.131 – 0.907]	0.009
Children					
Asia	0.067	0.093	6	[-0.115 – 0.249]	0.471
West Europe	0.479	0.065	6	[0.353 – 0.606]	<.0001

The general meta-analyses demonstrated the relevance of the environmental pathways in the transmission of *norovirus* in both the mixed (overall OR=1.800; 95% CI: 1.247 – 2.601) and the children population (overall OR=1.568; 95% CI: 1.158 – 2.125; Table 5B). On average, the mixed population attending to day care in the Netherlands (overall OR=1.831; 95% CI: 1.145 – 2.924) bore a similar level of risk of acquiring *norovirus* as people drinking spring

water or from local water supply in Serbia and Taiwan (overall OR=1.752; 95% CI: 0.969 – 3.171). However, in children from Vietnam, drinking water from well or other sources was not as strongly associated to *norovirus* infection (overall OR=1.102; 95% CI: 0.879 – 1.379). A significantly higher level of risk of *norovirus* infection in children was born by the pathway of attending day care/kindergarten in Vietnam and the Netherlands (overall OR=1.317; 95% CI: 0.955 – 1.813). On meta-analysis, children appeared equally likely to acquiring *norovirus* infection when living on a farm in the Netherlands, Vietnam or Mexico (overall OR=1.637; 95% CI: 1.182 – 2.265) or when playing in a padding pool or sandpit in the Netherlands (overall OR=1.545; 95% CI: 1.351 – 1.765 in Table 5B). Publication bias in the children data set was likely since the measures of OR were found to depend upon the case-control study size ($p=0.003$; Table 5B), although funnel plots presented an acceptable dispersion of observations (Figure 7).

Table 5B. Meta-analyses of environmental pathways for acquiring *norovirus* infection in the mixed (n=6) and children (n=13) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed (4 stud)	All environment	0.588	0.188	6	[0.221 – 0.956]	0.002
	Fixed effects					
	Day care	0.605 ^a	0.239	2	[0.136 – 1.073]	0.011
	Drink water	0.561 ^a	0.302	4	[-0.031 – 1.154]	0.063
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=4)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.4567	p=0.386		p=0.910	
	Publication bias	0.0076	0.0103			0.462
	Points removed	0				
Children (4 stud)	All environment	0.450	0.155	13	[0.147 – 0.754]	0.004
	Fixed effects					
	Day care	0.275 ^b	0.164	3	[-0.046 – 0.595]	0.093
	Drink water	0.097 ^a	0.114	4	[-0.128 – 0.321]	0.399
	Farm	0.493 ^c	0.166	4	[0.167 – 0.818]	0.003
	Playground	0.435 ^c	0.068	2	[0.301 – 0.568]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.455
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=9)		QM(df=4)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.2932	p=0.027		p<.0001	
Publication bias	0.0007	0.0002			0.003	
Points removed	0					

Figure 7. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of environmental pathways as risk factors for *norovirus* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right). Circle markers belong to OR measures with potential for bias

Most of the data recovered from primary studies within the pathways of transmission corresponded to person-to-person contagion, amounting to 20 ORs for the mixed population and 17 ORs for the children population. The contact with an ill person at home or outside home suspected or known to have *norovirus* is a very important risk factor of disease, as confirmed by meta-analysis in all of the geographical regions: Asia (pooled OR=12.98; $p < .0001$), North Europe (pooled OR=2.768; $p = 0.008$) and Western Europe (pooled OR=2.375; $p = 0.001$ in Table 6A). Since in all regions, this route of transmission was significant, no geographical region was removed when adjusting the general meta-analysis. As a whole, adults who had contact with any *norovirus* infected person within or outside the household presented 3.010 times (95% CI: 1.707 – 5.474) greater risk of contagion than those who did not. Children were much more susceptible to acquiring *norovirus* by direct transmission, since the pooled OR of person-to-person contagion for children (overall OR=6.430; 95% CI: 3.766 – 10.97; Table 6B) was significantly higher than that of the mixed population. In this data partition, only one potentially-biased OR turned out to be an influential data point in the meta-analytical regression, and was therefore removed. The corresponding funnel plot (Figure 8) did not hint any presence of publication bias, although the formal test evidenced a strong effect of study size on the measured association between person-to-person contagion with *norovirus* infection ($p = 0.003$ in Table 6B).

Table 6A. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of *norovirus* infection by region for the combined mixed (n=20) and children (n=17) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed and children					
Asia	2.563	0.367	6	[1.843 – 3.283]	<.0001
North Europe	1.018	0.381	14	[0.272 – 1.766]	0.008
West Europe	0.865	0.242	17	[0.391 – 1.339]	0.001

Table 6B. Meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of *norovirus* infection in the combined mixed (n=20) and children (n=17) population

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Both	Fixed effects					
(6 stud)	Children	1.861 ^b	0.273	17	[1.326 – 2.395]	<.0001
	Mixed	1.102 ^a	0.289	20	[0.535– 1.669]	<.0001
	Before 2000					0.790
	Random effects					
	s ² _u (Intercept)	0.2106	QE(df=34)		QM(df=2)	
	s ² (residual)	0.8538	p<.0001		p<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0003	0.0001			0.003
	Points removed	1				

Figure 8. Funnel plot of the meta-analysis of person-to-person transmission of *norovirus* infection in the combined mixed and children population

Apart from person-to-person transmission, *norovirus* infection can spread indirectly through contaminated food. In Northern Europe, food appeared as an important vehicle of transmission of *norovirus* in the mixed population (pooled OR=19.36; p=0.001), whereas the same cannot be said for Western Europe (pooled OR=1.261; p=0.200 in Table 7A). On meta-analysis, Asian children bore greater risk (pooled OR=3.004; p<.0001) of becoming infected with *norovirus* through food consumption than South American children (pooled OR=0.745; p=0.065; Table 7A).

Although the geographical regions were distinct between the mixed population and children, the general meta-analyses showed that, overall, children from China, Vietnam and Mexico were more likely to acquire *norovirus* infection (overall OR=2.751; 95% CI: 0.910 – 8.323) from food consumption than the mixed population from Switzerland, UK and the Netherlands (overall OR=1.332; 95% CI: 1.153 – 1.542; Table 7B).

Table 7A. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring giardiasis by geographical region in the mixed (n=8) and children (n=14) population

Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed					
North Europe	2.963	0.911	3	[1.176 – 4.748]	0.001
West Europe	0.232	0.181	5	[-0.123 – 0.587]	0.200
Children					
Asia	1.100	0.101	8	[0.903 – 1.297]	<.0001
South America	-0.295	0.160	6	[-0.609 – 0.018]	0.065

Table 7B. Meta-analyses of food pathways for acquiring giardiasis in the mixed (n=8) and children (n=14) population – no geographical region removed

Pop	Parameters	Mean	Standard error	n	95% CI	Pr > t , Z
Mixed	All foods	0.287	0.074	8	[0.142 – 0.433]	<.0001
(3 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Beverage	0.034 ^a	0.256	2	[-0.467 – 0.535]	0.894
	Produce	0.001 ^a	0.500	2	[-0.977 – 0.980]	0.998
	Seafood	0.820 ^b	0.285	3	[0.262 – 1.378]	0.004
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=4)		QM(df=3)	
	s^2 (residual)	1.1874	p=0.171		p=0.040	
	Publication bias	0.0021	0.0008			0.013
	Points removed	0				
Children	All foods	0.809	0.490	12	[-0.152 – 1.770]	0.098
(3 stud)	Fixed effects					
	Unspecified	1.513 ^b	0.139	5	[1.150 – 2.327]	<.0001
	Meat&chicken	-0.295 ^a	0.160	6	[-0.609 – 0.018]	0.065
	Before 2000					ND
	Random effects					
	s^2_u (Intercept)	0.0000	QE(df=9)		QM(df=2)	
	s^2 (residual)	0.1307	p=0.792		P<.0001	
	Publication bias	-0.0016	0.0010			0.114
	Points removed	0				

While, on meta-analysis, seafood – encompassing fish, oysters and whelks – was a strong determinant of *norovirus* infection in the mixed population (overall OR=2.270; 95% CI: 1.300 – 3.967); neither beverage (mineral water and juice; overall OR=1.034; 95% CI: 0.627 – 1.707) nor produce (salad and raw berries; pooled OR=1.001; 95% CI: 0.376 – 2.664) could be proven to be important vehicles of transmission of *norovirus*, probably due to the very few ORs recovered in these two subcategories (Table 7B). Averaging over case-control outcomes from China, Vietnam and Mexico, children who consumed market food, uncooked food or food eaten out (categorised as “Unspecified” in Table 7B) presented 4.540 times (95% CI: 3.158 – 10.25) greater probability of acquiring *norovirus* infection than those who did not. By contrary, meat and chicken were not found to be a vehicle of transmission of *norovirus* in children (overall OR=0.745; 95% CI: 0.544 – 1.018). After Cook’s distance assessment, no potentially-biased OR popped up as influential point. Whereas the funnel plots revealed an acceptable distribution of observations in both meta-analyses (Figure 9), the formal test of study size effect hinted that some case-control studies of small sample size may have remained unpublished due to their “failure” to find significant association between food consumption and *norovirus* infection in the mixed population ($p=0.013$; Table 7B).

Figure 9. Funnel plots of the meta-analyses of food consumption routes of transmission as risk factors for *norovirus* infection in the mixed (left) and children population (right)

In addition, separate meta-analyses were adjusted to the food categories of “Unspecified” food, “Seafood” and “Beverages” with no distinction of population, so as to aggregate the very scarce information that was available. In China and Vietnam, people who consumed market food, ate outside, uncooked food or suspicious food had on average 3.86 times (95% CI: 2.16 – 6.89) greater probability of becoming infected with *norovirus* than people who did not (Figure 10). The overall risk of acquiring *norovirus* infection by consuming seafood in UK, China and the Netherlands was lower, although still significant, at a pooled OR of 2.37 (95% CI: 1.42 – 3.96; Figure 11). It is worth mentioning that in the UK the consumption of oysters (OR=18.30; 95% CI: 1.50 – 223.3), whelks and winkles (OR=20.50; 95% CI: 1.60 – 262.6) bore higher risk of disease than the consumption of fish in the Netherlands (OR=1.80; 95% CI: 1.00 – 3.24; Figure 11). In the case of beverages (Figure 12), mineral water (OR=1.00; 95% CI: 0.46 – 2.17) and sweet beverages (OR=1.06; 95% CI: 0.55 – 2.04) could barely be associated with *norovirus* infection in Switzerland while in a case-control study from Vietnam, drinking bottled water was found to increase the odds of acquiring disease in children.

Figure 10. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the association between *norovirus* infection and consumption of unspecified food in the mixed and children population

Figure 11. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the association between *norovirus* infection and consumption of seafood in the mixed and children population

Figure 12. Forest plot of the meta-analysis on the association between *norovirus* infection and consumption of beverages in the mixed and children population

The main results from the meta-analyses on risk factors and pathways of exposure were compiled by means of two forest plots: one forest plot was built for comparing among the *global* risk categories as potential determinants of *norovirus* (Figure 13) and the other forest plot for comparing among *disaggregated* risk categories and specific pathways of exposure (Figure 14). To visually distinguish the most important routes of transmission, the pooled ORs listed in the forest plots were ranked by mean's decreasing order, and to assess the reliability in the pooled ORs, the number of ORs used in the computations were displayed.

Figure 13. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring *norovirus* infection for global risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The global risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

For *norovirus*, the global categories amenable of meta-analysis were only six for the mixed population and four for children (Figure 13). Among those, the most important risk factors in the mixed population were host-specific factors (i.e., suffering from immunosuppression or being organ transplant recipient; pooled OR=3.72; 95% CI: 1.66 – 8.36) and person-to-person contagion (pooled OR=3.01; 95% CI: 1.71 – 5.474), which bore discernibly higher association with *norovirus* infection than foods as a whole (overall OR=1.57; 95% CI: 1.24 – 1.98) and seafood (pooled OR=2.27; 95% CI: 1.30 – 3.97). While the environmental-related pathways of transmission were determinant of *norovirus* infection in the mixed population (pooled OR=1.80; 95% CI: 1.25 – 2.60) – yet to a lesser extent than seafood – the animal-related routes of exposure were, overall, not statistically associated with *norovirus* infection (pooled OR=1.20; 95% CI: 0.56 – 2.58).

In children (Figure 13), direct transmission person to person (overall OR=6.43; 95% CI: 3.77 – 10.97) was the most important route for acquiring *norovirus* infection, followed by suspicious food (pooled OR=2.75; 95% CI: 0.91 – 8.32). Nonetheless, it should be born in mind that the food consumption routes were meta-analysed using case-control studies conducted in China, Vietnam and Mexico, and hence they may not be applicable to Europe. While the environmental-related pathways of transmission were determinant of *norovirus* infection in children (pooled OR=1.56; 95% CI: 1.16 – 2.13) – yet at a significantly lower association with disease than that of person-to-person contagion – the consumption of meat and chicken, as a whole, was not associated with *norovirus* infection in children (pooled OR=0.74; 95% CI: 0.54 – 1.02).

Zooming into the disaggregated risk factors (Figure 14), it became evident that suffering from a chronic immunosuppressive disease (overall OR=8.17; 95% CI: 3.26 – 20.47) was an important predisposing factor for acquiring *norovirus* infection in the mixed population, followed by person-to-person contagion (overall OR=3.01; 95% CI: 1.71 – 5.31) and consumption of seafood (overall OR=2.27; 95% CI: 1.30 – 3.97). The odds of acquiring *norovirus* from drinking water (overall OR=1.75; 95% CI: 0.97 – 3.17) was comparable to that of the host-specific factor of suffering from other medical conditions (overall OR=1.65; 95% CI: 0.77 – 3.53); while having pets in the household was not found to increase the odds of infection with *norovirus* in the mixed population (overall OR=0.67; 95% CI: 0.54 – 0.83).

Figure 14. Forest plot summarising overall odds-ratios of acquiring *norovirus* infection for disaggregated risk categories, ranked in decreasing order. The disaggregated risk categories presented are only those made up of at least n=3 ORs

In children, direct transmission person to person (overall OR=6.43; 95% CI: 3.77 – 10.97) is the most important route for acquiring *norovirus* infection, followed by consumption of unspecified suspicious food (data from China, Vietnam and Mexico; overall OR=4.54; 95% CI: 3.16 – 6.53). The environmental exposures of living on a farm, attending day care and drinking water were, overall, important routes of transmission of *norovirus* in children. Children living on a farm (overall OR=1.64; 95% CI: 1.18 – 2.27) were as exposed to *norovirus* as those attending day care (overall OR=1.32; 95% CI: 0.96 – 1.81); whereas drinking water bore only a minor association with *norovirus* infection (overall OR=1.10; 95% CI: 0.88 – 1.38). Whilst keeping poor handwashing habits (overall OR=1.78; 95% CI: 0.63 – 5.04) could not be proven to be a factor facilitating the infection with *norovirus* in children, consuming beef and chicken was not found to be a source of disease (overall OR=0.74; 95% CI: 0.84 – 1.02).

4. Conclusions

4.7 Meta-analysis on risk factors for sporadic *norovirus* infection

- ❖ The outcomes from 14 case-control and cohort studies investigating association of sporadic *norovirus* infection with different routes of exposure were meta-analysed, taking into account geographical region and period of study.
- ❖ Very limited data was available for travel, the various animal routes of exposure, the environmental routes of drinking, recreational and waste water as well as consumption of seafood.
- ❖ The top three determinants of *norovirus* infection in the mixed population are: the host-specific factor of suffering from a chronic immunosuppressive disease (OR=8.17), direct person-to-person contagion (OR=3.01) and consumption of seafood (OR=2.27).
- ❖ In the mixed population, the odds of acquiring *norovirus* from drinking water (OR=1.75) is comparable to that of the host-specific factor of suffering from other medical conditions (OR=1.65).
- ❖ In children, transmission person to person (OR=6.43) is the most important route for acquiring *norovirus* infection, followed by consumption of unspecified suspicious food (China, Vietnam and Mexico; OR=4.54).
- ❖ In both populations, mixed and children, person-to-person contagion (OR=3.01 – 6.43) is more important a risk factor for acquiring *norovirus* infection than the environmental routes of transmission as a whole (OR=1.57 – 1.80).

- ❖ Children living on a farm (OR=1.64) are as exposed to *norovirus* as those attending day care (overall OR=1.32; 95% CI: 0.96 – 1.81) whereas drinking water bears only a minor association with *norovirus* (OR=1.10).
- ❖ Poor handwashing habits (overall OR=1.78; 95% CI: 0.63 – 5.04) could not be proven to be a factor facilitating the infection with *norovirus* in children.
- ❖ Routes of exposure that had no association with *norovirus* are: contact with pets in the mixed population (OR=0.67); and consumption of beef and chicken in children (OR=0.74).

5. References

5.7 Fourteen case-control and cohort studies assessing risk factors for *norovirus*

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